

**UNITÉ DE FORMATION ET DE RECHERCHE
DES SCIENCES ÉCONOMIQUES
ET DE GESTION (UFR-SEG)
BPV 43 ABIDJAN**

PUBLICATION 4

N'dri, K.L., (2017), "Stock Market Development and Economic Growth in Cote d'Ivoire: An ARDL Approach", The Empirical Economics Letters, Volume 16, Number 2, 2017 Issues. pp. 185 à 194

- Page de garde avec numéro d'identification ISSN
- Tiré à part de l'article

The Empirical Economics Letters

A Monthly International Journal of Economics

ISSN 1681-8997

Indexed in *EconLit* and included in *Cabell's Directory*

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March 2017

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Stock Market Development and Economic Growth in Côte d'Ivoire: An ARDL Approach

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Abstract: This paper investigates the relationships between stock market development and economic growth in Côte d'Ivoire and draws recommendations for market regulators. The study uses annual data on economic growth, stock market capitalization, inflation and foreign direct investment over the period 1990 to 2014 and tests for the long run and short run relationships among these variables within the framework of the ARDL bounds testing procedure. The findings support the hypothesis of long run relationship between stock market capitalization and economic growth whereas there is no short run relationship. This result is useful for market regulators since better market access policies will position the stock market as an alternative vehicle for investment and economic growth.

Keywords: Stock market development, economic growth, ARDL.

JEL Classification Number: O16, O47, C52

1. Introduction

The contribution of financial development to economic growth has been extensively studied over the past years (see, for example Levine, 2005 for a summary of theoretical and empirical overview of studies) but studies on the extent to which stock market development can spur economic growth are recent. The major motivation for these studies stems from the fact that, theoretically, stock market development can contribute to economic growth in several ways. First, stock market enables resource mobilization at reduced cost in the capital market thereby promoting investments that will be conducive to economic growth (Greenwood and Smith, 1997). Second, a well functioning stock market will promote the trading of financial assets given its liquidity and, enable market participants to hedge and diversify their risk while facilitating the exchange of goods and services. These contributions would in turn result in a more efficient allocation of resources thereby promoting economic growth (Arestis et al., 2001; Creane et al., 2004). However, existing empirical studies on this relationship have produced mixed results.

Tests of the relationships between stock market development and economic growth range from positive (Atje and Jovanovic, 1993 ; Levine and Zervos, 1998; Mohtadi and

Agarwal, 2004; Hondroyiannis et al., 2005; Nieuwerburgh et al., 2006; Enisan and Olufisayo, 2009; Masoud and Hardaker, 2012; Miguel et al., 2013; Balago, 2014; Nguyen and Pham, 2014 amongst others) to negative or insignificant (Harris, 1997; Azarmi et al., 2005; Naceur and Ghazouani, 2007; Wang and Ajit, 2013; Owusu and Odhiambo, 2014 to name a few) with different data and methodologies.

On the positive contribution of stock market development to economic growth for example, Levine and Zervos (1998), found that stock market liquidity was positively and significantly related to the future rates of economic growth. Their study was carried out on a cross section of 42 countries from 1975 to 1993. In a study of 42 emerging markets over the period 1995-2006, Masoud and Hardaker (2012) found that stock market development has a significant positive impact on economic growth. Miguel et al. (2013) studied the case of Portugal over 1993-2011 and found a bidirectional causality between the stock market and economic growth. Balago (2014) in a study on Nigeria over 1990-2009 reported that stock market capitalization had a positive impact on economic growth. Empirical evidences on the negative impact of stock market development on economic growth are diverse as well. In India, the study by Azarmi et al. (2005) for the period 1981-2001 reported an inverse relationship between stock market development and economic growth, particularly for the post liberalization period. The study by Naceur and Ghazouani (2007) for 11 Middle East and North Africa countries over the period 1979-2003 revealed that the relationship between stock market development and economic growth was insignificant. A Study in China over the period 1996-2011 by Wang and Ajit (2013) revealed a negative relationship between stock market and economic growth. Owusu and Odhiambo (2015) showed that in Ghana, stock market policies were not conducive to economic growth.

In light of the conflicting views exposed above, it appears that the question of the relationships between stock market development and economic growth is primarily an empirical one. The objective of this paper is to contribute to the existing literature by examining the long run relationships between stock market development and economic growth in Cote d'Ivoire over the period 1990 to 2014 using the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach to cointegration. The contribution of this paper is threefold: first, there is a long run relationship between stock market capitalization and economic growth; second, in the short run, inflation is harmful to economic growth but not in the long run; third, foreign direct investment has a positive impact on economic growth in the short run but at delayed rate.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents an overview of the regional stock market. Section 3 describes the data and, section 4 outlines the empirical methodology. Section 5 discusses the empirical results and, section 6 concludes.

2. Overview of the Regional Stock Market

The regional stock exchange of West Africa, known as the BRVM is the only stock market which is common to the 8 countries of the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) which are Benin, Burkina Faso, Cote d'Ivoire, Guinea Bissau, Mali, Niger, Senegal and, Togo. It was established on December 18, 1996 as a result of the transformation of the Cote d'Ivoire stock market created in 1973. It is charged with organizing and operating the securities market. Its responsibilities towards that end include but not limited to ensuring the listing and quotation of securities as well as the dissemination of information and the promotion of the securities exchange. The BRVM is headquartered in Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire with a national branch in every member State. It is a centralized spot exchange driven by orders with quotation done by the technique of *fixing* that is a single price results from matching bid and ask orders. The BRVM 10 composed of the ten most active companies on the exchange and, the BRVM Composite that comprises all securities listed on the exchange are the two indexes of the market. The determination of indexes obeys the methodologies of the FCG index of the International Finance Corporation, a World Bank affiliate. The trading system of the BRVM automatically generates indexes and circulates them after every session. The BRVM 10 is rebalanced four times a year whereas the BRVM Composite is reviewed further to every new listing. Stocks and bonds are the major securities and as of December 2016, 43 companies are listed on the BRVM.

3. Data

The data used in this study have an annual periodicity running from 1990 to 2014. Data on the growth rate of the per capita gross domestic product noted here as GDP and stock market capitalization as a percentage of GDP noted SMC are taken from the *Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis*. Data on the foreign direct investment net inflows as a ratio of GDP known here as FDI and the inflation rate note INF are sourced from the *World Bank Development Indicators 2015*. The growth rate of the per capita gross domestic product (GDP) in domestic currency is used as an indicator of economic growth. In general, three measures are used to capture stock market development, these are, stock market turnover, stock market traded value and, stock market capitalization which translates the market's ability to mobilize funds and contribute to risk diversification. Following Levine and Zervos (1996), I favor the stock market capitalization ratio (SMC) over the two other measures for two reasons. First, stock market traded value complements stock market capitalization since it reflects liquidity which is already catered for by market capitalization, even though a large market capitalization might not systematically translate into large trading; Second, stock market turnover also complements stock market capitalization given that a large and inactive stock market will be characterized by large

market capitalization but with low turnover ratio. Inflation (INF) is taken here as the first differenced natural logarithm of consumer price index. Inflation reduces the general purchasing power and therefore not conducive for investment. High inflation will negatively affect production since production factors will be high. Foreign direct investment net inflows as a percentage of GDP (FDI) is expected to positively affect economic growth under some circumstances such as acting as a vehicle for international technology transfer. Finally it is worth noting that the data go back to 1990 because the BRVM is a product of the transformation of the Cote d'Ivoire stock exchange created in 1973. Further, of the existing 43 companies listed as of December 2016, more than 90% are from Cote d'Ivoire.

4. Methodology

4.1. The Model

The basic model that I use to test for the impact of stock market development on economic growth is as follows:

$$Y = f(SMC, CV) \tag{1}$$

where Y is the growth rate of the per capita GDP which is function of the stock market capitalization ratio (SMC) and a set of control variables (CV) that contains the inflation rate (INF) and, the foreign direct investment net inflows ratio (FDI).

While putting emphasis on the stock market capitalization as indicator of stock market development and, considering the data description above, the functional form of equation (1) is the following:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 SMC_t + \alpha_2 INF_t + \alpha_3 FDI_t + \varepsilon_t \tag{2}$$

where Y_t is the growth rate of the per capita GDP. SMC, INF and, FDI are defined as above. Meanwhile, I expect SMC and FDI to be positively related to economic growth thereby confirming their positive contribution to economic growth. Their degree of significance will however tell which one contributes the most. As explained under the data section, the expected sign on Inflation (INF) should be negative; ε_t is the error term assumed to be to white noise; α_i are coefficients.

4.2. ARDL Bounds Test for Cointegration

In order to analyze the long run relationships and the short run dynamic interaction among economic growth, stock market capitalization, inflation and, foreign direct investment variables, I make use of the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing cointegration technique developed by Pesaran and Shin (1999) and further improved by Pesaran et al. (2001). This approach is superior to major cointegration approaches such as the two-step procedure of cointegration of Engle and Granger (1987) and, the full

information maximum likelihood approach of Johansen (1988) and Johansen and Juselius (1990) for four reasons: first, it is applicable regardless of the order of integration of variables, that is, either I(1), I(0) or mutually cointegrated. Second, it solves the endogeneity and issues of regressors variables and the inability to test hypotheses on the estimated coefficients in the long run. Third, it enables estimation of both long run and short run parameters simultaneously. Fourth, it provides better statistical properties in small samples.

The ARDL representation of equation (2) to examine the long run and short run relationships can be expressed in an unrestricted error correction model (UECM) as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = \phi_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \phi_{1i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \phi_{2i} \Delta SMC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^p \phi_{3i} \Delta INF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^q \phi_{4i} \Delta FDI_{t-i} \quad (3)$$

$$+ \gamma_1 Y_{t-1} + \gamma_2 SMC_{t-1} + \gamma_3 INF_{t-1} + \gamma_4 FDI_{t-1} + \mu_t$$

where variables are defined as before; $\Delta(\cdot)$ is the differential operator; $\sum(\cdot)$ is the summation operator and, μ_t is the error term assumed to be White noise. The second part of equation (3) with $\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \gamma_4$ refers to the long-run parameters and the first part with $\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4$ bears on the short-run parameters. The null hypothesis of absence of cointegration is given by: $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = \gamma_3 = \gamma_4 = 0$ and, the alternative hypothesis of $\gamma_1 \neq \gamma_2 \neq \gamma_3 \neq \gamma_4 \neq 0$ designates the existence of cointegration among the series in equation (3). The hypothesis test is carried out with a F-statistic. When the computed F-statistic is superior to the upper critical bound provided by Pesaran et al. (2001), it implies that series are cointegrated. In case the calculated F-statistic is below the lower critical bound, there is absence of cointegration. When the calculated F-statistic lies between the upper critical bound and the lower critical bound, there is a situation of inconclusiveness on cointegration. The lag structure (m, n, p, q) needed to apply the ARDL bound testing procedure is determined by the Schwartz Bayesian criteria whereby the minimum values are selected.

After estimation, I carry out diagnostic tests for serial correlation, functional form of the model, normality of residuals and, white heteroscedasticity.

5. Empirical Results

5.1. Unit Root Tests

Though ARDL bounds testing procedure is applicable regardless of the order of integration of series, it will be unreliable if series are integrated of order two or higher. I therefore carry out test for the order of integration using the unit root test of Phillips and Perron (1988) to ensure that series are not integrated of order two or higher and that the

dependent variable is integrated of order 1. I conduct the test using the model with constant and trend for the level series and, the model with constant without trend for the series in first difference. Table 1 tabulates the results.

Table 1: Results of Unit Root Test

Model with intercept and trend at level				Model with intercept and trend at difference			
GDP	SMC	FDI	INF	Δ GDP	Δ SMC	Δ FDI	Δ INF
-3.1403	-2.6615	-2.1379	-3.9713	-8.1355	-4.2636	-5.9986	-10.6742
NS	NS	NS	S	S	S	S	S
5 % critical value is -3.6121 at level.				5 % critical value is -2.9980 at difference.			

Note: GDP, SMC, FDI and INF are growth rate of per capita GDP, stock market capitalization ratio, foreign direct investment net inflows ratio and inflation rate respectively, $\Delta(\cdot)$ is the difference operator; S denotes stationary and NS nonstationary.

The results from the Phillips and Perron (PP) Unit root test show that all the variables in first difference are stationary as all PP statistics are lower than the critical value of -2.9980. However, for series in level GDP, SMC, FDI are non stationary and INF is stationary. This result also confirms that the dependant variable GDP is integrated of order 1 and, the stationary character of series in difference underlines the absence of integration of order two or higher. This mixture of stationary and non stationary series along with corollary conditions makes the series good candidates for the application of the ARDL bounds testing procedure to determine whether there exist long run relationships among variables.

5.2. Bounds Test for Cointegration

Equation (3) is estimated using the ARDL bounds test methodology with lags determined by the Schwartz Bayesian Criterion. Estimations results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Bounds Test F-Statistics

Equation	F statistic	Critical values		Cointegration
		Lower bounds	Upper bounds	
GDP/SMC, FDI, INF	6.5185	4.29	5.61	Yes

Note: GDP estimated with respect to SMC, FDI, and INF.

Table 2 clearly shows that when GDP is expressed as a function of SMC, FDI, INF, the null hypothesis of no cointegration is rejected at the 1% significance level as the calculated F-statistic of 6.5185 exceeds the Upper bounds critical value of 5.61. This result is an indication of the existence of long run relationships among variables. In light of the suggested long run relationship, it is worthwhile to estimate the long run and short run coefficients.

5.3. Long Run and short run estimates

Estimates of long run and short run coefficients are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Long Run and Short Run Estimates

	Long Run Estimates			Short Run Estimates	
	Coefficients	p values		Coefficients	p values
Constant	-0.4620	0.4407	Constant	-0.4620	0.4407
SMC	0.1081	0.3845	ΔSMC	0.1081	0.3845
INF	-0.4904	0.0005	ΔINF	-0.4904	0.0005
FDI	0.8817	0.1794	ΔFDI	0.8817	0.1794
			ΔFDI(-1)	3.4656	0.0009
			ECM(-1)	-1.0146	0.0001

Note: ECM(-1) denotes the coefficient of the lagged error correction term; * and ** denote significance at the 5% and 1 % levels respectively.

In the long run, it appears from Table 3 above that the coefficient on SMC is positive and significant at the 5% level thereby corroborating the earlier finding of long run relationship between economic growth and stock market capitalization. On the contrary, inflation (INF) has the expected sign but is not significant. This is in line with the conventional view in macroeconomics that permanent and predictable changes in the rate of inflation are neutral in the long run as they will not affect real activity. Foreign direct investment has a negative sign but not significant. Even so, this result might suggest that foreign direct investment might not contribute to wealth creation in the long run if not allocated to investments conducive to economic growth or if not enabling technology transfer. In the short run, the coefficient of the change in stock market capitalization (ΔSMC) is positive but not significant. This translates the fact that in the early stage, the stock market does not contribute substantially to economic growth. The coefficient on the change in inflation (ΔINF) is negative as expected and furthermore significant at the 5% level. This is in line with the view that above a given threshold, inflation becomes harmful to economic activity (Fischer, 1993; Barro, 1997; Khan and Senhadji, 2001 among others). The coefficient on the change in foreign direct investment is positive but insignificant whereas the coefficient on the change of the lagged foreign direct investment is positive and significant at the 1% level. This result suggests that the effect of foreign direct investment on economic growth is not immediate. Its effects are delayed for at least one year. The coefficient on the error correction model (ECM(-1)) is negative and significant at the 1% level as expected. It translates the fast adjustment rate whereby any deviation from the mean is quickly corrected. Finally, I conduct diagnostic tests and report the results in Table 4

Table 4: Diagnostic Tests

Hypotheses	Tests	p values
Normality	Bera-Jarque	0.2719
Serially uncorrelated	Breusch-Godfrey	0.9626
Homoscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.6101
Functional form	Ramsey RESET Test	0.2018

Note: * denotes insignificance at the 5 % level. All p values reject the null hypotheses.

Table 4 shows that tests of normality, absence of serial correlation, homoscedasticity and, functional form do not reject the null hypotheses thereby implying that the model is properly specified.

6. Conclusion

This paper has examined the relationship between stock market development and economic growth in Côte d'Ivoire. The study uses annual data on the per capita growth rate of GDP, stock market capitalization ratio, foreign direct investment ratio and inflation rate over the period 1990 to 2014 and tests for the long run and the short run relationships between stock market development and economic growth within the framework of the ARDL bounds test methodology. The results reveal that stock market development does affect economic growth in the long run but not in the short run. Inflation is neutral in the long run but has a negative impact on economic growth in the short term. Over this period, foreign direct investment is not significant for growth in the long run but it does positively influence economic growth in the short run at a delayed rate. Disequilibrium in economic growth is quickly corrected as shown by the negative and significant coefficient on the error correction model.

Finally, the study has important implications for market regulators in the sense that improving market policies in terms of access and protection of investors will position the stock market as an attractive alternative vehicle for investment and an engine for economic growth.

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